

TECHNISCHE
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DRESDEN

Naming convention for bioimage data

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General rules for saving

Structure of folders on the server (only temporary for inbetween storage) similar to OMERO! That means, only a two folder hierarchy for imaging data (Project folder → Data set folder → Images).

General rules for writing

Task	Notation	Example
to separate different categories	Underscore (_)	20240613_cell01
to separate within a single category	Space ()	mitotic spindle scaling
As acquisition date	YYYYMMDD	20240613

The following characters have to be avoided: () [] {} / \ # μ @ % & ° ; , | < > ä ö ü

Naming of project folders

Structure	Example
organism_project	C. elegans_mitotic spindle scaling

Naming of datasets

More than one condition per dataset (as defined in the glossary) are allowed.

Light microscopy data

Structure	Example
acquisitiondate_strain_condition1_..._condition6_microscopymethod_expID (expID = up to you) for pre-experiments: acquisitiondate_strain_condition1_condition2_microscopymethod_expID	20191018_tmr31_wildtype_LLSM_exp04 20240611_CRL-4000_monastrol_pre-experiment_CLSM_MK002

Electron microscopy data

Structure	Example
T#_strain_condition1_..._condition2_sampleID-block_sampleID-cell_microscopymethod_CellCycleStageNumber	T0596_CRL-4000_monastrol_blockF_cell08_TOMO_metaphase01 (for cells) T0596_N2_ani-2(RNAi)_wormA_cell01_TOMO_metaphase01 (for worms)

Naming of images

Light microscopy images

Structure	Example
<code>explD_acquisition date_“up to you”</code> <u>for pre-experiments:</u> In the “up to you”-part you can add all variables from your pre-experiment.	<code>Exp37_20230615_2cell_AB1</code> <code>MK002_20240611_monastrol_2mM_60min_live cell</code>

Electron microscopy images

Structure	Example
<code>T#_sampleID-block_sampleID-cell_grid#_section#</code>	<code>T0649_blockF_cell08_grid08A_section01</code> (for cells) <code>T0649_wormA_cell01_grid07B_section01</code> (for worms)

Glossary

Any new entry to this list has to be discussed and agreed upon by the whole research group.

Organism/cell type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C. elegans • A. rhodensis • HeLa • RPE-1 • P. apterus 	
Projects	See experiment categories in CFCI-eLabFTW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Male meiosis • Spindle scaling • Monopolar spindles 	
Strains	See categories for cell lines and worm strains in 'resources' in CFCI-eLabFTW.	
Conditions	Condition	Example
	Genetic condition	wildtype, NuMA, CRISPR, ...
	RNAi treatment	ani-2(RNAi)
	Chemical/drug treatment	monastrol
	Pre-experiment	time point, incubation time, concentration, ...
	Cell stage	metaphase, anaphase, 2cell, 16cell, meiosis I, meiosis II, ...
	Sample status	living sample, fixed sample
Microscopy methods (LM)	BF	Brightfield microscopy
	DF	Brightfield microscopy with darkfield contrast
	DIC	Brightfield microscopy with differential interference contrast
	PH	Brightfield microscopy with phase contrast
	WF	Widefield microscopy with fluorescence
	CLSM	Confocal laser scanning microscopy
	SD	Spinning disk microscopy
	LSM	Light-sheet microscopy
	LLSM	Lattice light-sheet microscopy
	MP	Multi-photon microscopy
	FLIM	Laser scanning microscopy with fluorescence live time measurement

Microscopy methods (EM)	TEM	Transmission electron microscopy
	TOMO	Transmission electron microscopy of a tilt-series
	FIBSEM	Focussed ion-beam scanning electron microscopy
	SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
	STEM	Scanning transmission electron microscopy
SampleID-cell (EM)	Cell number on the section cell01, ...	
SampleID-block (EM)	Block number before sectioning blockA, wormB, ...	

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concept

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